

SOME MODERN CHALLENGES AND PROBLEMS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES AT UNIVERSITIES

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ABSTRACT

Shortcomings in teaching foreign languages at universities today. problem solving using modern and innovative technologies and foreign literature.

This study explores and identifies some reasons for the problems of foreign language learning (English) and teaching from the perspective of instructors and learners using the case study model. The data of the study was gathered by a semi-structured interview form, and the study group of the research was composed of English language instructors and graduate students at Ahi Evran University. Random sampling method was used to determine 15 instructors and 20 graduate students to face-to-face interview, and the data of the study was analysed by content analysis method, which the students and instructors agreed on students who have been problematic in language learning process. In addition to students, examination systems, instructional programs, language teachers' qualifications and learning environments have been considered as barriers to language learning. On the other hand, students and instructors suggested starting learning/teaching English earlier, much more practice and exams on all four skills; elective courses; more practice and communication; revisions in teacher training system, considering individual differences; motivating and encouraging students; and designing well equipped language environment and teaching materials

Today, in every developing country, there is rapid development in all areas. Innovative technologies are always being developed in the technical field, and they are developing in the medical and legal and other fields. However, it is important to keep in mind that each and every field requires advanced and skilled professionals. The majority of the bubbles are graduates of higher educational institutions. Nowadays, foreign languages are of great importance in higher education. Foreign language can provide an additional solid foundation for future graduates of higher education institutions. However, today there are several methodological and linguistic deficiencies in teaching foreign languages in higher education institutions.

Methodological and linguistic disadvantages include inaccurate teaching methods in a variety of formats, lack of computational material, and so on. If we list and analyze these problems one by one, the following are:

- Lack of materials and books translated into foreign language by specialty in the course of the teaching process, incomplete and full use of innovative technologies;
- Lack of practice hours to encourage students of higher education in the learning process, not teaching a student to think in a foreign language
- No new or effective exams have been developed to test students' foreign language proficiency, non-use of modern innovative technologies;

It is desirable for every qualified and experienced teacher to have a pre-written course plan, manuals and books in a foreign language related to the syllabus. These materials help the student to learn his / her specialty in a foreign language and provide further information when using the literature of the advanced countries.

Each theoretical course and the student with theoretical knowledge can apply their theories in practice. For this purpose, it is a very good way to teach students to think freely, to hear from each student, to form small groups and debate them on the topic. This is because a student who has an opinion and is able to express himself can make a contribution to the development of the country by presenting himself with suggestions.

One of the most important processes is to pass exams on these topics. Exams are an important factor in assessing students' knowledge of how well they are. It is important that the student assessment is comprehensive. I hope that using foreign exam methods such as IELTS, TOEFL, B1, B2 and other foreign exam methods to achieve a good level of foreign language proficiency will be very effective.

In my opinion, it is important for every teacher and student to increase their focus on foreign language in higher education and to find more effective solutions to the abovementioned issues. To this end, I believe in a holistic approach to teaching and learning about the problems and shortcomings of the teaching process, that the student is interested in the course and that in the future, he or she will be well-trained.

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